

FROM THE PEN OF ABDUR RAHIM KHAN E KHANAN¹

In India, from early medieval period, the art of book making existed. Variety of hand written books, despite weather problems, have survived till our time. Abdur Rahim Khan-e-Khanan (b.

¹ Prof. Chander Shekhar, Department of Pesian, Faculty of Arts, University of Delhi, Delhi.(A precise form of this paper is published in the spl Vol. Celebrating Abdur Rahim Khan-e-Khananan, Mapin India, 2016) Present paper is updated with more detail. 2. This painting is from Yale Arts Gallery, Yale Univ. Credit goes to the said Gallery and thanks to Madam Emyi Potter of the said gallery.

1556 AD) was brought to Akbar's court when he was just four years old (see the picture V&A museum Akbar Nama; MU, 694/1; AN, 132/2), after Bairam Khan's assassination at Patan, from where the family of the assassin was first taken to Ahmedabad by the trusted lieutenants of the deceased. In the personal care of the emperor Akbar, Abdur Rahim got his education in different spheres at the hand of the best teachers of various fields including fine arts like calligraphy from Mohammad Andijani, Mian Wajihuddin Gujarati, Nizamuddin Badakhshi, Shah Fathullah Shirazi, Hakim Ali Gilani and Jalaluddin Mohammad Dawwani. (MU, 539/2) At the age of 16, his administrative career started from Patan, a place where his father was killed, when he accompanied Akbar to Gujrat. After a short stint, he became governor of Gujrat in 1576. His continuous success begged him many royal favours and elevation in rank and file. He ventured from Jaunpur to Bhakker, Sindh and Thatta, then to Malwa and Deccan where he spent almost 22 yrs –with a gap of almost two years when he was suspended from the royal services –but again asked to take up Deccan assignment. (MU, 708/1) Abdul Baqi Nihwandi and other contemporary of this great lover of art and literature have covered number of aspects which highlight on the fine characteristics of this great personage. It tells that he was patron of many poets and writers as well as the men of writing and artisans of book making. His knowledge of various languages led him to get royal favours as well as interaction with local intellectual class. His close relations with scholars of various languages or sub-languages enriched his knowledge on various aspects which can be gleaned from his prose and poetry, available in different languages. His movements from one state to other –Gujrat-sindh-Malwa to Deccan – also brought him to the proximity of Indian culture and diverse style of life as well as different language. His administrative and royal duties also facilitated him to quench his thirst for literary and fine arts. He created a rich and valuable library splurge with books on various subjects. The author of Mathirul Umra enumerates his all the qualities and characteristics for nurturing Persian, Sanskrit and Hindwi as well as Arabic literature and also fine arts, especially Calligraphy, Painting- both the pivotal art of Book Making. Though, John Seyller stated the exact location of the great library is not known but MR provides clue about the library's existence in various cities wherever AK stayed. There is also ample information about the people who joined the literary court as well as worked in the library of AK from his first library which was in Ahmedabad. Kami Sabzvari and many others who were poets as well as the library officers. They even used to get their compositions corrected by AK (488MR) and the copy was kept in the library. Mir Baqi was the librarian at Ahmedabad when he left for Iran his son Abdussalam became the head of the library. After his short stint at Malwa or Seronj, he shifted for almost two decades to Burhanpur, where he not only constructed various buildings –Gardens, his own palace, the Maqbaras for his son Shah Nawaz Khan and also library. Quddasi says that Sheikh Abdussalam was the librarian (p.146, Khandesh under Mughals) . When the library was in Seronj Mulla Boqai was the librarian and Mir Bakhshi Agha Muhammad Shirazi was the Darogha of the library. His library- according to an estimate, it had 24000 books -was rich due to the

excellent artisans and men of pen working in it.. He himself was excellent expert in recognizing the valuable books which were in the form of manuscripts. His writings on various manuscripts in the form of notes or memoirs or the detail about the characteristics of a book and his own drafted royal edicts all speak for his love for the books.

Many writings and sources -from past and present writers – speak on formation of the said library, its books, its artisans, procurement of books, value and valuation of books, conservation and preservation of books and presentations of the books prepared in the said library and also the location of library –Ahmedabad, Seronj, Agra, Burhanpur- and many valuable holdings manuscripts and writings of Khan e Khanan in various libraries and museums. Naik (pp. 278-79 and appendixes), Ahmad (1925, Kolkatta)², Rahmat Ali Khan³ and John seyeller⁴ has listed some notes and writings, preserved in some libraries and museums. But still there are some which have not been highlighted by above writers. In the present paper, some of his notes and a letter which are on manuscripts are reproduced and discussed in the light of the contents.

His notes on various manuscripts, like on Khamsa-e Amir Khusrau, speaks about the title and author of the work, its then holder, way of procurement, the person who was deputed to procure from the holder, the value, paid for the procurement. The physical state, if it is damaged or need conservation, the person/s whom the task of conservation was assigned and the date of its inventory into the library of the said lover of books, i.e. Abdur Rahim Khan e Khanan. He was a master calligrapher in *Naskh and Nastaliq*.⁵ His hand written notes exhibit his such mastery.

The number of the books which is estimated by many about 20-24k seems to be right. One can estimate the number from the writings of Nihawandi who quotes in his anothology on the poets and other men of art of book binding that their works (*Mussawide*) are preserved in the library of Siphesalar. In the course of many, he also mentions that Khan e khnana even made corrections in the poetic compositions of some poets (for instance ,maulana Kami Sabzvari, p 488 or Maulana Qaderi p. 60). But the known or existing books on which notes of Khan-e Khanan is found are very few as some listed by the afore said scholars. Some letters or royal edicts which he wrote to his contemporary grandees or the royal court or the petition which were sent by him especially to the court of Jahangir are available in the hand of other scribes.

Some manuscripts having his own handwritten notes speak of many features, ranging from the art of bookmaking to the state of mind of the seller or previous possessor as well as the

² Nazir Ahmad, Shamsul Ulama, Hafiz, ,” Note on the Library of Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khanan, The First Prime Minister of the Emperor Akbar, University of Calcutta,Journal of the Department of Letters vol. XVI, Calcutta University Press, 1927 (I am thankful to Dr. Mehmood Alam for providing me a copy of this article)

³ Rahmat Ali Khan, Lalit, Salar Jung Library, Hyderabad, The Grand Court of Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khana, 27-39

⁴ John Seyeller,” The Mughal library And Painting Workshop,” *Artibus Asiae*, 1997, (p55-56)

⁵Rahmat Ali Khan. P.28

difficulties the collector had to face or the court rivalries of which Khan-e Khanan had to face an inquiry headed by Mahabat Khan, though the latter had risen in the rank and file in nobility only in Jahangir's period. Likewise, the cost of the precious books, fabulously illustrated, especially from the brush of Behzad or painters like him or the calligraphers like Mir Ali Tabrizi or Sultan Ali Mashhadi.

This great lover of books left behind large number of information on various subjects in his own hand writing, . Very few from that huge collection we have today in the form of his notes, letters or some missives. Here under, some notes of Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khanan are reproduced from different manuscripts available in various libraries in India and abroad.

In the end of the year, 991 (1583) when the news of taking over of the city of Ahmedabad by Sultan Muzaffar Shah Gujrati reached Akbar at Allahabad, he dispatched an army led by young 28yrs old Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khanan, addressed at that time as Mirza Khan to crush the imperialistic desire of Sultan Muzaffar. Mirza Khan, on the advice of Daulat Khan, an afghan commander, led the Mughal force against mighty force of Sultan Muzaffar in Muharram, 13, 992 (AH) and defeated him at the battle of Serkhej with his small contingent. There are many Fathnamas and verses composed in praise of Mirza Khan (=Khan-e Khanan) for this victory. Amongst the books, for ethical and moral training, Gulistan and Bostan of Sheikh Sadi (d. 691 AH/1291AD) has been must as a

primer.

There are three mss bearing the note of Abdur Rahim Khan-e-Khanan in Rampur Raza Library, Rampur . The first one seems to be the earliest, in view of its date, note by Khan-e Khanan on any book, reached to us.

1. Kulliyat-e-Sa'di,(dated 938 AH/1532), Ms. no. P.3224b.

A beautifully decorated and illustrated copy of Kulliyat-e-Sadi (Ms. No.P. 3224 b) comprising of 390 pages with some illustrations which were added later on⁶was transcribed in Shiraz in the month of Ramazan, 938. This copy was brought to Mirza Khan by Ali Mardan Bahadur⁷, after his victory over Sultan Muzaffar Gujrati, in Gujrat(at Serkhej) as he himself appended a note stating:

الله اکبر

در گجرات بعد از فتح سلطان مظفر گجراتي علي مردان بهادر ک..هدیه {کرد} تاریخ نهصد و نود ودوي هجري

حرره عبدالرحيم ابن بيرم {عفي عنها}⁸....

از اول تا آخر مطالعه {کردم} بلکه انتخاب هم نمودم. فقط⁹

In the same hand, there is also a verse of Jami:

گر مشک خواند خاک درت

برخ گهر به طعن

In the above note, apart from information about the occasion when the said manuscript was gifted, he also adds after, putting his name –Abdur Rahim Ibn Bairm – that he studied the work and also made a selection from it. Thus, he would have prepared a work on the basis of Guistan himself too.

In the central part of this flyleaf, there is another important note from the pen of Munim Beg, Khan-e Khanan, another important noble of Akbari Court. According to this noteThe note, dated 976 AH (1568-69) was sent to him (*faqir*) written in Dar-us Saroor¹⁰ Jaunpur , by the dear wife

⁶Barbera S. and Desai, Z, Mughal and Persian Paintings and illustrated mss in the Raza Library, Rampur, p.193.

⁷ He became Subedar of Berar later on in Jahangir's period. During hisSubedari, many Persian poets, like Maulana Jamaluddin Muhammad Mulhimi who was son of the renowned Alim and saintly person, KhwajaKamaluddinShirazi was in his court. Mulhimi was also granted a Jagir in Berar. When Ali Mardan died during the retreat of forces after skirmishes with Malik Amber, in 1612.Mulhimi then joined the court of Khan-e Khanan. See, MR, p. 342-344 ; Naik, 345;

⁸On all the notes, one may find this complete wordings.

⁹ The heart/pan shaped word, a mark of the end of matter, a sign showing writer as an humble one, is in shikasta font.

¹⁰Burhanpur is also mentioned as Dar-us Saroor.

(al-aziz Kuj/Kuch) of Bahadur Khan Ali Khan The note also provide the detail about the contents of the work. This flyleaf has four Arz-dida(s) and some seals while few are also defaced¹¹.

These notes and arz didas and seals and its present location (holder) exhibits the importance given to this copy of Kulliyat-e-Sadi. Following are the decorated opening –illuminated with the name of Sheikh Sadi -and last folio-providing the date 938 AH- of the afore said copy of Bustan:

¹¹ See also the catalogue of Rampur Raza Library, (note by JanabArshi Sahib) and also Barbara & Desai, p.194.

صالح الدین سعیدی

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ
شکر و سپاس معبودی را
جلت قدرته که انبیا
مخلوقات عالم است
در روزی دهسند بنین
و نبات آدم کریمی که خوان نعمتش
بر مطیع و عاصی و دانی

صالح الدین سعیدی

کسی در دستم باشد هم تو این طبل بزن تا آواز برسد
من همان بماند فوجی است که در اینزه که مرا طبل خوان
نیزنی که آواز تیر من کم شود هر کت گفته از من است
ازت تو بنان می تیرنی که آواز طبل کم می شود

تم الکلیات افصح المتکلمین و المقتدین بشیخ نفع الیقین
سعدی شیراز سپه رفته اند علیه و تاریخ
شهر رمضان المبارک پنده شام
شمسین و تسبیح و صلی الله علی
خیر خلقی محمد و آله الطیبین
و الطاهرین
العالمین
۲

کسی گفت مردمان
بجوایب تمام
بکام خصاری
بستید و ببول
رفت و اینها بی
عصار را در

دومی ناله گم
دو پویه داد

بهر آن روغت که از دست

پسته بود و نه گرش
صفت گفت پای
ست این پای را گشت
ار و من که گاه و پای

1. Another work,(Ms. No. 755) is Munajat-e Khwaja Abdullah Ansari, in the beautiful Nastaliq calligraphic hand of Sultan Ali Mashhadi, dated 921 AH also has a hand written note of Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khanan. The note which is as below is the oldest than other notes:

اللَّهُ اكْبَر

در تاریخ 35 الهی موافق 998 هجری این کتاب داخل کتابها شد که دور و وری زمانه باین بیچاره سپرده...
دوست بندگان و خاک پای ایشان عبدالرحیم الن بیرم عفی عنه

بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم

تاریخ نسبت و نیم ماه بهمن الهی موافق
نیم مهر جماد الثانی سنه ۱۰۳۰
جلوس مبارکست داخل بناگاه
این یارمند درگاه سدر منور
شاه جهان این جهانگشا بنابر

در تاریخ سنه الهی موافق
۱۹۹۸
در میان کور دور و در راه
نام بخار به سرده دو دست مکان
و خاک باران غنم ارض هم این
محمد سرم علی و همها

۵۰۶۱۸۶۹
۱۹۰۱۱۹۵

اصول العباد
نصیر المصالح

سازمان تعلیم و تربیه

سازمان تعلیم و تربیه
کتابخانه مرکزی
تاسیس ۱۳۰۲

سازمان تعلیم و تربیه
کتابخانه مرکزی
تاسیس ۱۳۰۲

بدر

حاجت ز بکریت قصه تپت کج پر سے ان صحت
 کہ بعد از آن معلوم از عرش و کریت سے ان معد و پت
 افریدوں عرش تپت سر کہ تو را احتجاجش کوید
 پست نوری از خود در سپان ما را از خود بریاں
 الی سلطان محبت تو را سپرد دل نشت لباس آرام
 درید و کشتی صبرت الی هر چه بیا میر پدا از ما پت
 کہ بر ما پت ان حدیث با چکانه چکانه و با اشنا شناس پت

کاتب
 محمد بن محمد
 در مدینه منوره

الله أكبر ۲۲ ابریکه لاء من دیدہ شد

Apart from the above stated note of Khan-e Khanan, this exquisite ms bears the autographs of Jahāngīr, Shāhjahān and Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khanan too. Jahangir's note dated 1023 AH/1614 states that the ms is copied by the renowned calligrapher, Sultan Ali Mashhadi (see the colophon as attached):

رسالة خواجه عبدالله انصاري خط ملاسلطان علي از پيشکش خان خانان بتاريخ ۲۴ جمادي الاول سنة ۱۰۲۳
حررة جهانگير ابن اکبر بادشاه

Another note is by Shah Jahan, dated 1037 AH/1629 AD which is as follows:

بسم الله الرحمن الرحيم
بتاريخ بيست و پنجم ماه بهمن الهي موافق بيستم شهر جمادي الثاني سنة ۱۰۳۷ هجري، روز مبارک.. داخل کتابخانه اين
نياز مند درگاه شد حررة شهاب الدين محمد شاه جهان ابن جهانگير شاه ابن اکبر شاه:

Two oval shaped seals of Shāhjahān and Aurangzīb read as:

These are some of the important notes in the hand of elite nobles of Mughal and post Mughal nobility of 18th c. appearing on the fly-leaf:

3. The third manuscript is the copy of Majalis us Ushshaq, Ms. No. 2295. As the colophon (see the attached copy of the illuminated last folio) says, it is a work of Sultan Husayn, Kamaluddin ibn Sultan Mansur ibn Mirza Baiyqara ibn Mirza Umar Shaikh ibn Amir Timur. He mentions that the work is prepared on moral and ethics and expect when the successors will read it they will remember him.

The flyleaf note which bears many notes and arzdīd (sa) as well seals has a note of Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khan stating:

در تاريخ روز جمعه غره شهر ذي الحجه الحرام 999 داخل کتابخانه عالي نواب کامگار گردون افتدار
سپهسالار خان خانان بن نواب رضوان جاىگاه محمد بيرم خان شد در مقام بکر

Under the same note there is an addition in the same hand:

مجالس العشاق از خواجه شيه محمد ابتياع نموده شد. قيمت اين كتاب دو صد و پنجاه رويه

In 999AH/ 1591AD, on Friday, 1st of month of Ziul Hijj it is entered in the library of Nawwab Kamgar Gardoon Iqtedar Siph-salar Khan-e Khanan bin Nawwab Rizwan Jaigah (who is worth getting a place in the paradise) Mohammad Bairam Khan –e-Khanan, at B(h)akkar (Sindh).

Majali us Ushaq is purchased from Sheikh Muhammad

Price of this book is of Rs.250/-

Amongst other Arz Dida Shud (transaction attestation) and seals, one is from the time of Shah Jahan just on the right hand side of this note, dated 16th Farwardeen, 10 Ilahi.

This ms, comprising of 473 folios is scribed, illuminated and adorned with 51 illustrations/miniatures in Shiraz school.¹²

¹² See also Barbara, p. 197-199

سقا است مثل مر این هم
سیوم ه

در دوم دوم خ

سایح اراغ العالی
عوض دین

بازدم عرض دین

بشایح و غیره
عوض دین

مشایخ و غیره
عوض دین

۶۶ داود دین

۶۶ داود دین
عوض دین

عوض دین

عوض دین
۹۲۴

۵۰۸

بشایح و غیره
عوض دین
مشایخ و غیره
عوض دین
مشایخ و غیره
عوض دین

نواب کامکار کرد
رضوان جانکاه
مجالس عشاق
قیمت این کتاب

عوض دین

عوض دین

در عشق تو چسند آنکه سو زیم احس
 نت الی پاله الموسوم بجالش العشق من تصنیف
 حضرت سلطان اطلین الافاق مابلارث
 والایستحق ابو العازی سلطان چین مبادرخان
 نادر الله و برمانه بعون الله الملك الحلاق والصلوات
 و السلام علی پند محمد وآله الذین کانوا کاشفین
 فی الاشراف صلوة دائمة ایله یوم النفاق

سر آنکه نام من از راه سینکوی ببرد
 همیشه در دو حبان نام او پینکی مابد

طیعت آنکه ازین
 شده برین شام
 قیامت آن زین کینه
 آب کشیده هانوش
 ت و عطا یا موم
 ت فیض فضل اولایز
 بل او علی الدوام از حبه
 از چشم قد علم کل
 جلی و استعداد
 بر قد سر کس طهرزی
 ن از ان سخنان در دما لست
 سر زوزیم احس

There are certain Ms which has only signature of Khan-e Khanan, or information about the inventory of a work in the Library of Khan-e Khanan as stated below:

الله اكبر

۰۰۰درشبي كه شنبه سنة ۱۰۱۹... به كتابخانه نورديده... متعلق ساخت . حرره عبدالرحيم

On *Shish Risāla-i-Sa'dī* Ms. No. 9, Bankīpūr Collection Khuda Bakhsh Library, Patna.. The colophon indicates that it was transcribed by Mīr 'Alī al-Kātib in 944 A.H. It has an interesting note regarding perjury by some one as stated in the note by Shah Jahan himself. According to this note It was the transcription of Mīr Bāqir not of his father as some one erased his name and foully tried to project it was a work of his father:

الحمد لله الذي انزل علي عبده الكتاب حرره شهاب الدين محمد صاحب قران ثاني شاهجهان خط باقر پسر ملاء علي است نام اورا تراشیده نام پدر نوشته اند¹³.

There are two seals bearing Muhammad Rahīm b. Muhammad Bairam and Abul-Muzaffar Muhyiuddīn 'Alamgīr Pādshāh. The Ms. is written in a beautiful and clear Nasta'liq with in gold and coloured borders with a small decorated heading at the beginning. An 'Arz-Dīda on the fly-leaf reads as:

بتاریخ شهر جمادی الثانی ۹۸۶ در مقام ادیبور عرض شد.

In Indian subcontinent, works of Firdausi and Sa'di became important base for learning and calligraphic achievements, A copy of Bustan, in beautiful calligraphic hand of Shah Sawar, prepared for Sultan Nasir Shah bin Ghiyas Shah bin Mahmud Shah Khalji of Malwa in 908 AH is preserved in the rich collection of National Museum, New Delhi vide no. 48.6/4. It has 43 beautiful illustrations. This copy of Bustan has note by Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khanan:

در ایام محاصره احمدنگر.... خورداد الهی سنه 25 (جلوس اکبری) و اواخر ذیقعد 1001. حرره عبدالرحیم (بن بیرم، عفی عنه)¹⁴

Amir Khusrau's works, especially his Khamsa and historical masnawi Duwal Rani wa Khizr Khani got prominence amongst the lovers of Persian poetry and painting for its subject matter in beyond the then border in Persianate world. A manuscript of Khamsa in the state library of Berlin (MS.Or.1278, fol.3)¹⁵, which once belonged to the library of Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khanan as the round seal having two round circles. While the outer circle decorated with flower petals of different shapes and the inner one peaks of its holder:

¹³ Prof Nazir Ahmad, p. 18

¹⁴ Prof Nazir Ahmad, p58. For illustration , I am thankful to Manuscripts section, National Museum, New Delhi)

¹⁵ It is registered erroneously as Diwan-e- Amir Khusrau, in the catalogue of the state library of Berlin. (The note is on folio.1r)

Around this seal there is a lengthy note by Khan-e Khanan himself as at the end of 'the following note which has his signature , " written by Abdur Rahim Ibn Muhammad Bairam Ali Khan, " authenticates that the lengthy note on the Procurement of the Khamsa, as well as about his indictment on the basis of futile efforts of his contemporaries to ruin his career but with the devine help due to his ever-right performance and services rendered with all truthfulness, could be proved says:

الله اکبر

در سال هزار و دوازده ورقه چند از این خمسه نفیسه شریفه میر باقی سمرقندی از گجرات آمد و آورد و چون از باقی کتاب استفسار شد بعد از تجسس بسیار معلوم شد که یک کتاب با چند ورق دیگر پیش مرزا عبدالملک است.. انعام آدمیانه نموده ازو گرفتیم و تتمه کتابها را بعد از پرسیدن بسیار از هر کس شنیدیم که در گجرات پیش هر کس چند چند ورقه بوده است باز میر باقی را با دو سه هزار روپیه فرستاده شد که از پیش هر کس که باشد هر چه او خواهد داد ه آن اوراق بیارد بعنایت الهی چنان شد که تمام این پنج کتاب بدست {آرد} مگر ورقه چند که ضایع شده باشد ازین کتاب ده پانزده اوراق را شخصی داشت بگمان اینکه اگر خود بیارد و چیزی بیشتر بیابد. با چند کتاب دیگر از علما دیگر گرفته متوجه آگره شد و آن ایام بود که این غریب همراه مهابت خان تهمت زده بسعایت مقربان صاحب عرض بدرگاه رفته بود و از آنجا که نیت درست بود و راستی و جة کمال و دولتخواهی در درجۀ اعلی لطف الهی در صورت عنایت بندگان حضرت سلیمان مکانی ظهور یافته ازان بلایا خلاصی یافت:

اگر تیغ عالم بجنبد ز حال بزد رگی تا نخواهد خدای

معاینه دیده شد مجملآن مرد که اوراق این پنج کتاب را بکتابهای دیگر می آورده در راه دزدان آن ده دوازده ورق را بردند . هر جا این کتاب لطیف شریفی که خط مولانا سلطان علی و تصویر استاد بهزاد بود بتمامبرساند و..تصویرها که در آب افتاده بود آنهاآسیب دیده شد را اصلاح نمایند و آن ورق چند نیز که افتاده بود به محمد مومن {هروی}....امر کرد که بنویسد و جلدسازرا فرموده {شد} که زردوزی نمایند و حواشی را زیب و زینت بدهند تا آنکه ده دوازده سال کار می کردند تا باتمام رسید و این چنین که در ها می در آید در تاریخ هزار و بیست و شش {آماده} شد

حرره عبدالرحیم ابن محمد بیرم خان ،عفی عنها

The above note of Khan-e Khanan contains multiple information which can be gleamed through its wording. It states

"Mir Baqi Samarqandi¹⁶ came from Gujarat in 1012¹⁷(AH) and brought a few folios of this illustrious exquisite book of Khamsa (-e-Amir Khusrau). When about the remaining books of the

¹⁶ Nihawandi mentioned him as Mir Baqi MawaraunNahri. He states that he belonged to very renowned and prominent Saiyyed family. He managed the library of Khan-e Khanan at Ahmedabad during the Governorship of the latter. He was the recipient of many favors' for his laudable services and got elevation up to the rank of Darogha-e- Kitabkhane , Ma'athir-i-Rahimi: Section III: Biographies, Ed., Abdol Hossein Navai, Society for the Appreciation of Cultural works & Dignities, Tehran, 2002, (p. 936).

¹⁷In 1012AH, Khan-e Khanan was in charge of Berar and Telingana to conduct the campaign against Malik Amber (Naik, p.140) But

quintet was enquired at length, it came to know that one other book (of this quintet) along with some other folios (of the another book) is in the possession of Mirza Abdul Malik. We procured from his that book by honoring him with the suitable reward. In regard of the remaining books, it was resolved that suitable amount be given to every one who has as much as folios of this collection. Two to three thousand rupees for the procurement were sent to Mir Baqi so that he may give to the holder of the folios as per his desire for this purpose. For the Divine favour, it happened in this manner that all the five books were in the hand of a person, though some folios were destroyed. Another person who was possessing some –ten-fifteen- folios thought that if he will hand over those folios himself (to me) he may get more award.[Thus] He set forth for Agra with some more books which he procured from some learned people.

In those days this humble one, arraigned and slandered by the court confidants, had gone to the royal court along with Mahabat Khan. Since the intention was of integrity and truthfulness prevailed in the semblance of perfection (of my deeds) and perfect appearance of goodwill caused the divine favour (and these caused) ensured emergence of the favours of the Solomon seated His Majesty. Hence, I was relieved of the afflicted miseries (of the tantamount allegations) as observed:

Though the sword of world (ly people) rises from its state, but it merely hits on a nerve, as there was not will of God,

In brief, that person who had set forth with those twelve folios and some other books was robbed of those folios on his way by the highway robbers.

However, this exquisite noblebook, in the calligraphic hand of Sultan Ali Mashhadi and with the illustrations of Master Behzad became complete. Since the illustrations which had fallen in water and got water stained, ordered to be repaired. And some folios too which had also fallen in water were assigned to Mohammad Momin ¹⁸. The Jildsaz¹⁹ (the binder) was asked to put a binding with gold embroidery and also desired to adorn it with decoration. Since this task took to be completed in the span of ten-eleven yearsto come out in the present form in 1026 (AH).

Written by Abdur Rahim son of Mohammad Bairam, May God pardon him for his sins.

This folio also has a note of Shihabuddin Shah Jahan Badshah as well as oval shape seal of Aurangzeb Alamgir 1101 (AH). It also gives the number of folio 205 but the number of

¹⁸ Mulla Mohammad Momin Hirawi (d.1025AH) son of Shah Mehmood Hirawi, was a master calligrapher of *Nastaliq* –both *Khafi* (short) and *Jali* (long) hand -and artisan of book decoration). Nihawandi states that majority of the books of the library of Khan-e Khanan are in his hand.(P. 935-36, Ma’sir Bayani has given a list of his other works available in the libraries of Iran and else where(Pp.846-47, Ahwal-e- Khushnawisan...).

¹⁹ Though, the name of Binder is not mentioned. But it seems he may be Mulla Muhammad Hussain Hirwi, bother of Mulla Mohammad Momin Hirwi. He was an expert binder of his time, having speciality in Aks-Kari (?).

illustration and the figure amount stated under the word Qimat (price) figure has gone away with the brittle paper from that portion.

The note is written in 1026 AH from Burhanpur but the process started from Agra as it begins saying that in 1012, Mir Baqi brought the folios in Agra. Thus, this note covers a period of almost 14 years, though Khan-e Khanan states: it took 10-11 years to get back the book in complete decorated state. On his desire, remaining material of the manuscript was also procured.. He procures some other part of this work from Mirza Abdul Malik after making some suitable amount as well as from some others. He was given 2-3 thousand rupees for this purpose. Person who brought some books and some folios, out of which some were robbed off is not identified completely and how much money was paid to him is also not mentioned, though he had come to agra for this greed only.

The note states that the present work is scribed by the famous calligrapher Sultan Ali Mashhadi(844-926AD)²⁰and the illustrations/miniature paintings by Master painter Behzad. Interestingly, both Sultan Ali Mashhadi and Behzad were in close contacts. Bayani has quoted the following verse in which Sultan Ali Mashhadi's longing for his is visible:

فرزند عزیز ارجمندم بهزاد
گه گه گذرش
او عمر منست از ره صورت لیکن
برین طرف می افتاد
عمریست که از منش نمی آید یاد

My dear child, Behzad, comes some time towards this side, though he looks by appearance as old as I am, but it is long that he does not remember me.

The reference to conservation work of the manuscript highlight an important aspect. In Mughal Period, we find various such references and these exhibit the large scale work of restoration of the books. For instance, on a copy of Shah Nama of Firdausi 61.390, National Museum, New Delhi), a note by a renowned noble of Shah Jahan's court Muhammad Saleh, dated 3rd Rabi II, 1043 AH²¹ also provides the same information. (see Appendix I) preserved in This note also

²⁰Sultān 'Alī Mashhadī, master calligrapher of Nastalīq was at the court of Sultān Husain Mīrzā (873-911 A.H.) and his wazīr, Amīr 'Alī Sher Nawā'ī. His date of death is 926 A.H. but there are other opinions too.. Amongst his specimancalligraphy in Indian collections, following two are usually quoted:

i) Dīwān-i-Hāfiz (No. 817/54): Abdus Salām Collection, M.A. Library, AMU, 'Alīgarh. It is a good specimen of Nastalīq Calligraphy . The following is in its colophon:

”کتابه المذنب الی الله الغنی سلطان علی المشهدی“ .

ii) Munajāt-i-Khwāja Abdullāh Ansārī: This Ms. is preserved in the Razā Library, Rāmpūr (No. 755) and is a specimen of superb piece of Nastalīq Calligraphy. It is dated 921 A.H.. This one is discussed in the following pages too. See also: Nazir Ahmad, “*Timūrid Mss. of Artistic and Historical Value in Indian Collection,*” in Persian Manuscripts: Studies in Culture, Literature and the Arts, Ed. Chander Shekhar, Persian Research Journal, Dept of Persian, University of Delhi, Delhi, 2012, Pp. 1-61; For life and detail on his specimen: Bayani, Mahdi, “*Ahwal-e-Khushnawisan,*” Intesharat-e Imi, Tehran, 1363AH/1984AD, Pp.241-266, Vol.I

²¹ Chander Shekhar, *Lesser Known illustrated Mss. of Shah Nama in National Museum,* in , “*Textual Heritage: Persian Urdu & Arabic*” Ed. Chander Shekhar, National Mission for Manuscripts, New Delhi, 2011

highlight the important feature of the life of Khan-e Khanan too as he laments in this note. Though, he states that for his established integrity and unquestionable loyalty, his innocence was established and for the same, he got relief. . From various contemporary sources too, even in the period of Akbar, Asad Beg who was assigned to make arrangement for the departure of the wedded daughter of Adil Shah to the Prince Daniyal and bring back Muhammad Hussain Inju to the royal court states that Khan-e Khanan was being bribed by Adil Shah and Malik Amber to delay the departure of the Adil Shah princess, Sultan Begum (daughter of Ibrahim Adil Shah II (1580-1627);s fourth wife Sunder Begum²²who was from the Adil Shahi domain and to keep away Mughals from Deccan;²³. Following these consistent complaints, Khan-e Khanan was stripped of his administrative position. Mahabat Khan was entrusted to escort him back to the royal court at Agra in 1609 .On this issue, there is a correspondence between Khan-e Khanan and Mahabat Khan. The copies of these letters are available in the fly leaf of a manuscript no. Or.2678 (India Office Collection), entitled, Miscellaneous letters. (see the appendix II). According to this, Mahabat Khan was too convinced about the innocence of Khan-e Khanan. He also admits that his loyalty and truthfulness saved him from the royal wrath.:

نقل رقعہ کہ نواب مہابت خان بخانان نوشتہ

فلک متابع تو باد و بخت نیک سگال خدای ناصر تو باد و روزگار معنی

دعای باخلاص درست را بوظیفہ داری از لوازم زندگی بر خود واجب دانسته خدا نکند کہ بقوت و غفلت خود را مقصر شناسه و خود را میرا از دعای هوانان رسم و رسمیات کہ بجزویات صوری بازی ده طبیعت جانبین اند دانسته از قید های رسمی بوسیله راستی معنوی خود و شناخت عالی فطرتی نواب جیو نجات یافته تسلی میداشت

بہمہ وقت باغ شکر ترا بنواھا ہزار دستانم گر بتابم و خدمتت گردن مار بارازہ گریتانم

This letter and the following one which were in the response of a letter of Khan-e- Khanan, reveals the innocence of the latter. On the same flyleaf there is a letter written by Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khanan in his own handwriting. It states in its head line: نواب مذکور بخط خاص خود: کتابتی کہ نواب مذکور بخط خاص خود. بنواب اعتماد الدولہ نوشتہ اند.

نسبت بجای خود و عادت خود وفا و حقیقت خود و پیشنہاد راستی و دوستداری گلہ مندی را بیگانہ می بینم بازار ملا مقصود علی کہ کافر شدن و کفر گفتن و زنا آویختن و ناقوس نواختن بسیار بہتر باشد کہ شکوہ از ایشان بزبان آوردن ہر چند کہ فقیر زیور مردی و مردمی نگاہداشت غایت را پیشتر و بہتر از مجلس حضور کہ ہزازان دیار پرستی و دنیاداری با بسیار اعراض در دوستیہای حضور ہست کہ غایت ندارد پس چہ گنجایش دارد کہ پرستار محبت معنوی بودن و گلہ مند گشتن کہ تنگ قانون محبت من و قرار داد من باشد، از من بعمل آید اگر کلمہء درین باب در کتابت خواجہ ابراہیم حسین نوشتہ باشد دل و زبان آگاہی ازان ندارد. قلم ہیچ دخلی بدل و زبان ندارد و او برای جوانمرد است اگر قضا را بر سر صیقلی سخنی ماضی آمدہ واضح نمایم . ظاہراً کہ شکوہ ء فقیر خلاف طبیعت قرار داد ہمت و بلندی فطرت و

²² Shervani H.K. & Joshi, P.M, *History of Deccan*, Vol.I, Pp.293, 344

²³ .Asad Beg Qazvini, *Risala-e-Asad Beg Qazvini*, fol. 12, Tolboys, J & Macmillan, *European Travelers in India*, Calcutta, 1956, p,82; Afzal Hussain, *The Nobility under Akbar & Jahangir*, Pp.15-173, 1999

دانایی ایشان نباشد.... بلکه بسیار بد تشخیص یافته نزد عالی فطرتان حقیقت و وفاداری هیچ و پوچ اربابست. طبیعت حکیم کمال چنانچه فرزند ملا دهان شما که مرکب ملحق باشد بالین او شده بود و معزز سراز ز ادب بینی برآمده بود که فرشته جان بر ارحم بحان او آمده نظر بر فطرت عالی شما کرده بخشید. ظاهراً که محققان این وضع را بلند همتی و بزرگی طبیعت خود نام نهاده اند. چنانچه حکیم کمال که ایشان هم محقق و دانا بودند پس دوستان ظاهر حقیقت گو مروت گو و فاگو اگر داری نصیب جاده ما گو.. فقط

The above letter addressed to Nawwab Aitmadud Daula, nucleus of Iranian nobility, according to Afzal Hussain, (168, The nobility under Akbar and Jahangir, who also discuss the above issue at length), laments against those endeavored to defame him, despite knowing his integrity and loyalty. He especially mentions about Khwaja Ibrahim Hussain for misrepresenting to the royal court against him. He even complains against those of lower nobility who have risen in the time of Jahangir.

In brief, Khan-e Khanan's own statement reflects the deeper conflicts of interest in the court of Jahangir. Shahnawaz Khan, author of Ma'sirul Umra too states the chain events and concludes that in 20th regnal yr, Jahangir not only freed him of all the charges but also decorated him with many favours. Khan-e Khanan got encribed the following verse on a diamond and put in a ring:

دوباره زندگی داده مرا لطف جهانگیری ز تاییدات ربّانی

، دوباره خان خانانی²⁴

When Khan-e Khanan got the relief, Mahabat Khan who even got killed the second son of Khan-e Khanan, Iraj, in 1612 wrote a letter to the former when the royal court felt that injustice had been committed on the basis of the misrepresented reports against Khan-e Khanan as was realized that he is the only one who could handle carefully the Deccan debacle. He was honoured substantially, and dispatched to Burhanpur with a strong force to crush Malik Ambar's mischievous plans. Prince Khurram (later Shah Jahan) who was also sent as the command got married to the grand daughter (daughter of Shah Nawaz Khan²⁵, elder son) of Khan-e Khanan for securing motivated secured cooperation to thwart the bullish activities of Malik Amber and dubious role of AdilShahis of Bijapur. Alongwith the administrative and military role, Khan-e Khanan continued his academic pursuits as recorded by Nihawandi in MR.

In regard of the work, Khamsa-e-Khusravi which comprises of 225 folios with complete five masnawis of Khamsa has two folios 1v&2v at the beginning of later additions –most likely which are referred by Khan-e Khanan in his note_. These have 9 couplets in each while the remaining folios have 21. In the folios with the content of Matla'ul Anwar and the last book is A'ina-e Iskandari, which also has an illustration from the brush of Master Behzad. On 42r, the illustration seems to be later addition. All the folios have border with floral design, an addition

²⁴MU, p.706/II

²⁵ His tomb exists even today on the outskirts fo Burhanpur.

of later period. As Khan-e Khanan mentions in his note that the ms had fallen in water, it was given for restoration, fortunately, the central part saw the lesser damage. But the border and side area met the damage. It is that on not on a single folio one may find catchword.

It may be mentioned that there are some other mss too which were part of part of Khane – Khanan’s library. Like, one mentioned by Prof Nazir Ahmad²⁶ in State Museum, Patiala. This a Bayaz (collection of poetry from different renowned poets of Persian, like, Shaikh Attar, Maulana Rumi, Khwaju, Salman Sawooji, Shaikh Iraqi, Yamin and Shaikh Nizami, scribed in bold Nastaliq on gold ruled and colored bordered paper, which is richly illuminated. The scribe of the work is Humam ul Munshi Ul Murshadi, dated 849 AH. A hand written note of Khan-e Khanan dated 993 is as follows:

در تاریخ نهصد و نود و سه که در احمدآباد بود بعض از خدمتگاران را بجهت ابتیاع اسباب بهگوه فرستاده بود. از گوه حی حی... بهطریق پیشکش این کتاب را فرستاده بود و استدعائی که نموده بود موافق اراده اسباب مایحتاج رسید حرره عبدالرحیم بن محمد بیرم عفی عنه.

It is interesting to note that during his stay at Ahmedabad as Governor of Gujrat, as per this note, he sent people to buy valuable object to purchase from Goa. This copy was sent as Pishkash to him which is much suitable to his demands.

The following note also appears on the same page:

در وقتی که جهانگیر بادشاه این غریب را بهخدمت دکن همراه شاهزاده پرویز فرستاده من این کلیات نواب خانجهان بهبرخوردار عبدالرحیم الملقب خان عالم فرستادم.

It has a number of seals and ‘*Arz-Dīdasht*’ in the names of the nobles of the Mughal court such as Itimad Khān, ‘Anbar, Mansūr, Khān ‘Alam and others.

There is a copy of *Tarikh-e-Mahmood Shahi* (Manuscript no: 23/902) of Sharafuddin Muhammad, a history of Sultans of Gujrat especially on the period of Sultan Mehmood Beghra of Gujrat (whom the work is ascribed) in Arif Hikmat collection, King Abdul Aziz Library , Madina Munawwara, S.A. This copy too has a long note by Khan-e Khanan²⁷

In Maulana Azad Arabic and Persian Research Institute, Tonk²⁸, also one manuscript copy of *Murujul Zahab* (مروج الذهب) of the renowned geographer Masaudi. The writing is as follows:

²⁶ Opt.cite.P. 60-61

²⁷ This information is provided by Dr. Arif Nau Shahi who has seen this manuscript. I am thankful to him for this information. However, he did not provide further detail about the contents of the note or other codices detail

²⁸ T-1523/Ar. Ref. Jalali, S.F, *Taimuri MughloN ke Kitabkhano mein: Mohrein, TarqimeN aur ‘ArzDid*, P.149, Proceedings of the Conference on *Mohrein, TarqimeN aur ‘ArzDid*, 30th Sept.1994, Khuda Bakhsh Oriental Public Library, Patna

کتاب که مشهور بتاریخ مسعودی است موسوم به مروج الذهب محمد مومن تاجر که از پتن دکن بعد آن تحفه ابلاغ رسید (مورخه) ربیع الثانی ۱۰۲۰ راقم این حروف عبدالرحیم ابن محمد بیرم عفی عنها²⁹.

Apart from these, there are some books of Tafasir – Quranic Interpretation – and other sources of Islamic studies, in Salar Jung Museum, Hyderabad and else where, some of which are also listed by other scholars as referred above which explains many important events of the life of Khan-e Khanan.

There is another manuscript of his library which I traced in Bu Ali Sina Library, City Museum, Bukhara (near Lab-e Hauzi). The work, entitled Kunzul-Ummal, It has a full page in Arabic written by Abdur Rahim Khan-e-Khanan and sealed.

²⁹ The Muruj al-Dahab (Meadows of Gold and Mines of Gem) by al-Masudi is an historical account from the beginning of the world starting with Adam and Eve until and through the late Abbasid Caliphate and medieval Baghdad. It is widely known as Tarikh al-Kamil wa Bihamishihi Rawdat al-Manazir fi 'Akhbar al-'Awa'il wal al-'Awakhir, organised into several volumes, years, and subsections. Each volume is divided in chronological order into years. Each year has several sections committed to major events, which are not necessarily in chronological order. These subsections include major political events, the appearance of groups such as the Franks or the Tatars (Mongols), and major battles like the Siege of Jerusalem of 1099. It is published by Ahmad al-Halabi & Muhammad Mustafa, Cairo, 1303 A. H./ 1886. Above published text does not have any reference to the Ms. Copy of APRI, Tonk.

الله أكبر والحمد لله
 سنة ١٠٢٩
 No 60 (1100)

اتفق يوم سبت ايام بومع الادل الداخل في الف وعشرين وتس مجالته الك... ودموان العلماء
 الذين اجهموا كرمهم وهم يجتهدون فيها قوتهم وكان المجمع في بيتي والمجلس مشغول بالكتب العلمية
 من التفسير والحديث والحكمة والادب... اذ جاء كتاب كثر العمل الذي القه الشيخ الكامل الصبي
 في ترتيب الاحاديث وذكر ان هذا الكتاب عين كتاب صحاح الجامع الذي صنفه الشيخ الكامل
 بل ترتيبه وتبويب وتوزيعه عالم او عالم با در اكر حديث يعصم به وجرانه ويقع في تصديق
 كثير وتفتيش عديد واذ قور جدا الشيخ المتفق حال الكتاب هكذا شمر عن الحمد والاجتهاد وذيل
 وتوجه الى ترتيب الاحاديث ووضع كل حديث في موضعه الذي يليق به وتبويب
 وصوب وسماه كثر العمل والحق ان التوفيق بهذا الترتيب والتبويب ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله}
 للعلماء والقارئين عن التصديق ويعلم ان الشيخ الكامل الغافل المصنف ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله}
 هذا الكتاب حال خطاه الشريف بخط الغفلة وتوجه عليه في ما ظنم النقص ففهمت واحترت
 لخدمته الكتب ان استكتبوه واذا استكتبتم وكما وكم واحدا الى واحد ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله}
 فقال الشيخ ان اجعلوا استكتابكم بحوالي وكمل في رحمت من سنة احد وثلاثين ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله}
 وادار ايت قط المنقول مما احسن من كتابه المنقول جعلت المنقول هدية ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله}
 للشيخ الذي هو كاسم جبالا للعلم والفضل وخلف الشيخ دعاءه لي وشكرت الله سبحانه
 لتوزيع الكتب الحديثية عند اهل فخره ثم حمد الله عزه محمد الرحيم ابن محمد رمي ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله} ^{مقبول عند الله}

This valuable hitherto unknown hand written note of Abdur Rahim Khan-e Khanan is scribed in Arabic says: In the month of Rabi-ul-Awwal 1029 Ah/1628AD, an assembly of men of knowledge and most utmost respectful clergy those were exponent scholars of Hadith, Tafsir, Hikmat and literature was held at my house. During the discussion on various subjects, one of the respected scholar noticed the copy of Kunzu Ummal (Fi Sunnan ul Aqwal w Al-Afwal) , a work of great scholar Sheikh Alauddin Ali Mutaqqi Hisamuddin Burhanpuri. It is mentioned that the work actually based on Jame-ul Jawamai written by the great theologian Allama Jalaluddin Siyuti Misri (849-911AD). But the base work was unarranged and the readers face difficulty in finding their desire Hadis. Sheikh Mutaqqi arranged the work in a systematic and proper order

and entitled it Kunzul Ummal. This work is highly commandable and it facilitated the readers and the arrangement (now) save their time and energy.

Looking at Kunzul Ummal, Mian Jamal Muhammad, after a brief perusal of the work, contemplated to study thoroughly it. I realised his intention and asked the attendants of the library to prepare two copies of the same: one for me and other for the said Sheikh. The Sheikh offered to copy the work himself. Hence, the task of copying the book was completed (by him) in the month of Rajab, 1031AH (May, 1622 AD). I found the copied version was much better than the source work. Hence I gifted one to the Sheikh Jamal who was true to his name in knowledge and intelligence. Sheikh blessed me. I thanked profusely to Allaha and distributed the books on Hadis among the scholars. Thanks to the almighty, writer (of these lines) Abdur Rahim son of Muhammad Bairam.

Seal: (Text) The dust of the road of men of truth, Abdur Rahim

Above phrase is rare among the notes left by Abdur Rahim Khan e Khanan on different manuscripts. The Ms which is in octave size has 1052 folios having 27 lines on each folio. Almost every folio too have a seal of the endower Khwaja Yar Shah bin Mehmood of Bukhara year: 1224AH i.e early 19th c. It's binding in light red color has a golden color medallion in the centre with two shoot ups.

Above note is published by this author in his book, *Indian Cultural Imprints in Uzbekistan (2023)*³⁰

In brief, above specimen of Khan-e-Khanan's notes are of immense importance to read in between important detail of his time, his literary endeavors and people associated with him either as artisans, sellers, or the royal personages or even his rivals at the Mughal court.

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